

Geographical Study Of Sex Ratio In Beed District 2011 (M.S.)

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Abstract:

Population Geography is a branch of Human Geography, it has study population growth, its distributional pattern, Density, religious and linguistic composition, Sex ratio, age structure, migration, standard of living and economic structure etc. The aim of present paper is analyses Spatio-temporal changes of sex ratio in Beed district of Maharashtra state. The present study is based on secondary source. The secondary data collect from census of India, district gazetteers, statistical department, District Socio-economic Review and district statistical abstract of the Beed district etc. According to the 2011 census figure the total population of Beed district was 2585049 in which total population 1349106 are males and 1235943 are female. Thus the overall sex ratio of Beed district was 916 females per 1000 of males. The sex ratio of the Beed district declined continuously decade be decade since 1901-2011. It was declined 49 females per 1000 of males.

Key Word: Sex Ratio, Migration, Fertility, Mortality, Literacy

Introduction:

The male female ratio is a major attributes of demography. The pattern of sex ratio clarifies the employment situation, consumption pattern, social desires of the people and other socio economic features of a community (Shrivastri & Koshal,1998). In itself, the sex ratio is a function of three basic factors of sex ratio at birth, differential in mortality of the two sexes at different states of life and sex selectivity among the migrants (Clarke, 1960). The knowledge of sex ratio helps in understanding the psychological characteristics of a community (Chanda & Sidhu, 1979). The sex ratio is vital to the geographic analysis of an area for they are not only significant features of the landscape but also impact the other demographic features significantly and as such provide additional means materials for analysing regional landscape (Trewartha, 1953).

Objectives: To analyze the temporal changes of Sex ratio in Beed district.

To study rural-urban differentiation of Sex ratio in Beed district.

To study Special variation of sex ratio in Beed district of Maharashtra State.

Data Base and Methodology:

The present study is based on Secondary data. The secondary data is obtained from several sources which includes both published and unpublished books, government and private publications, district census handbook, Census of India, District gazetteers, statistical department, socio economic review and district statistical abstract of Study region district. Collected data is processed and presented in the forms of tabular and graphical methods and present in the maps and graphs. Sex ratio define the ratio between male and female per thousands of males.

Following formula has been used for calculate by sex ratio

$$\text{Sex ratio} = \frac{\text{Total number of females}}{\text{Total number of males}} \times 1000$$

Study Area: Beed district is located in the middle part of Maharashtra state and extend between 18°27' and 19°27' north latitudes and 74° 49' and 76°44' east longitudes. The east-west distance of Beed district is 268 kms and 127 Km width of the north to south district. Total Geographical area of the

Decadal Variation of Sex Ratio 1901-2011

district was 10693 sq. kms. and share 3.5 percent area of the Maharashtra state and 19.20 percent area of the Marathwada region. According to the 2011 census figure the total population of Beed district was 2585049 in which total population 1349106 are males and 1235943 are female.

Table No: 1 Decadal Variation of Sex Ratio 1901-2011

Decadal Variation of Sex Ratio in Beed and Maharashtra State		
Decade	Beed	Maharashtra
1901	985	978
1911	980	966
1921	963	950
1931	949	947
1941	941	949
1951	957	941
1961	969	936
1971	954	930
1981	965	937
1991	944	934
2001	936	922
2011	916	929

Source: District Census Handbook, Census of India.

Temporal Variation of given study describe the movement of sex ratio over period of time. According to the 2011 census figure the total population of Beed district was 2585049 in which total population 1349106 are males and 1235943 are female. Thus the overall sex ratio of Beed district was 916 females per 1000 of males. Thus the number of female is quiet less as compared to males in other words the sex ratio in the Beed district has always remained unfavorable to the female.

Decadal Changes of the sex ratio in Beed district of Maharashtra State from 1901 to 2011 Shown in Table No. 1. Beginning of the twentieth century sex ratio of Beed district was about 985 females per thousands of males and 978 in Maharashtra, thereafter showed continuous declined up to 1941 in Beed District and 1931 in Maharashtra. The sex ratio was decreased due to high mortality of females due to epidemics like plague,

cholera, influenza during the period of 1911 to 1931. In 1951 there was increase compare 1941 with sixteen points in Beed district, after independents in 1951-1981 the sex ratio of Beed district and Maharashtra state was up and down decade by decade. After that 1981-2011 the sex ratio of Beed district was declined continuously up to 2011, it was about 865 females per thousands of male and it was declined with 916 in 2011. It seems that male female ratio of Beed district and Maharashtra state was not favorable some last decades. In 1901-2011 the sex ratio was declined 69 points in Beed district and 49 points in Maharashtra.

Spatial Variation of Sex Ratio:

Spatial variation of the total, rural and urban sex ratio is shown in Table No-2. According to 2011, the sex ratio of Beed district was 938 females for thousands of males.

Table No: 2 Spatial Variation of Sex Ratio: 2011

Sex Ratio				
Sr. No.	Tahsil	Total	Rural	Urban
1	Ashti	925	923	962
2	Patoda	899	899	N.A.

3	Shirur (Kasar)	901	901	N.A.
4	Georai	921	918	944
5	Manjelgaon	912	900	928
6	Wadwani	902	903	894
7	Beed	912	908	928
8	Kaij	902	903	884
9	Dharur	912	908	931
10	Parli	922	915	937
11	Ambejogai	930	925	945
District Total		916	912	933

Source: Census of India, district census handbook Beed district 2011

It was not evenly distributed at one tahsil to another. It was observed that high sex ratio was found in Ambejogai tahsil with 930 females per thousands of males. Followed by Asti (925), Parli (922) Georai (821) and low sex ratio was observed in

Patoda tahsil with 899 females per thousands of males. Ambejogai, Ashti, Parli and Georai tahsils recorded above the tahsil average sex ratio but remaining district was recorded below the regional average.

Rural Urban Sex Ratio – 2011

According to 2011, the rural sex ratio of Beed district was 938 females for thousands of males it was lower than the urban sex ratio with 933 females per thousand males. It was also not evenly distributed at one tahsil to another. In rural area it was observed that high sex ratio was found in Ambejogai tahsil with 925 females per thousands of males. Followed by Asti, Parli, and Georai tahsil and low sex ratio was observed in Patoda tahsil with 899 females per thousands of males. In rural area Ambejogai, Ashti, Parli and Georai tahsils recorded above the tahsil average sex ratio but remaining district was recorded below the regional average. Spatial variation of the

rural and urban sex ratio is shown in Table No-2. Rural and urban sex ratio of the study region was not evenly distributed.

In the study area high urban sex ratio was observed in Ashti tahsil with 962 females per thousands of males and low sex ratio was observed in Kaij tahsil with 884 females per thousands of males. Ambejogai, Ashti, Parli and Georai tahsils recorded above the tahsil average sex ratio but remaining district was recorded below the regional average. In the study area urban sex ratio was higher than the rural sex ratio due to high literacy, better medical facility, nature of economy.

Conclusion:

The above study concluding that the sex ratio in the Beed district was not an even, it continuously up and down but its overall decreased decade by decade (1901 to 2011). Initially in the twentieth century, the sex ratio of Beed district it was 985 females per thousands of males and it was 916 females per thousands of males in 2011.

Spatial pattern of sex ratio was not evenly distributed at one tahsil to another. It was observed that high sex ratio was found in Ambejogai tahsil with 930 females per thousands of males. and low sex ratio was observed in Patoda tahsil with 899 females per thousands of males.

In the study area urban sex ratio was higher than the rural sex ratio due to high literacy, better medical facility, nature of economy. In rural area Ambejogai, Ashti, Parli and Georai tahsils recorded above the tahsil average sex ratio but remaining district was recorded below the regional average. In the study area high urban sex ratio was observed in Ashti tahsil with 962 females per thousands of males and low sex ratio was observed in Kaij tahsil with 884 females per thousands of males.

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